

A COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF BIODIVERSITY BETWEEN TROPICAL DECIDUOUS AND SAVANNAS IN EASTERN GHATS OF ANDHRA PRADESH, INDIA

S. Matyaraju¹, J. Ramalakshmana¹, V. Madan Mohan Rao², Y. T. Rajesh Babu^{1*}, S. B. Padal³

1. Research Scholar, Department of Botany, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam- 530003, Andhra Pradesh, India

2. Lecturer in Botany, Government Degree College, Chintalapudi, Eluru -534460, Andhra Pradesh, India

3. Professor, Department of Botany, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam- 530003, Andhra Pradesh, India

Abstract

This study examines the diversity of tree and herbaceous species in deciduous and savanna forests. In the deciduous forests, 31 tree species from 21 families were recorded, with Fabaceae, Malvaceae, and Combretaceae being the dominant families. In contrast, savanna forests hosted 23 tree species from 15 families, with Moraceae being the most diverse family. Both forest types shared 14 common species, while deciduous and savanna forests each had unique species. For herbaceous species, deciduous forests had 11 species across 9 families, with Asteraceae being the most diverse. Savanna forests had 13 herbaceous species across 9 families, with Malvaceae, Acanthaceae, and Asteraceae being the most diverse. Simpson's Diversity Index indicated slightly higher diversity in deciduous forests, while Shannon's Index and Margalef's Richness Index also favored deciduous forests, suggesting greater species richness and diversity. Conversely, savanna forests exhibited higher evenness. The study highlights that deciduous forests support a broader range of species and a more even distribution, whereas savanna forests have a slightly higher probability of encountering different species.

Keywords: Diversity, Tropical, Deciduous, Savannas, Forests, Eastern Ghats

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most climate-sensitive processes in forest ecosystems is disturbance (Seidl et al., 2020; Sebald et al., 2021; Ramalakshmana et al., 2023). Global change increases the pressure on forest ecosystems through changed environmental conditions, which in turn, alter ecological processes substantially (Trumbore et al., 2015). Tropical forests cover 7% of the earth's land surface, but harbor more than half of the world's species (Wilson 1988) and are currently disappearing at an overall rate of 0.8-2% per annum (May and Stumpf, 2000; Sagar et al., 2003; Ramalakshmana et al., 2023). Biodiversity is defined as the kinds and numbers of organism and their patterns of distribution (Barnes et al., 1998; Eshaghi Rad et al., 2009). Tropical forests are regarded as the world's most diversity-rich ecosystem (Sanders, 2006;

Sayer and Whitmore, 1991; Pratap et al., 2013; Reddy et al., 2008). The Relative growth rate (RGR) is lower in humid than in semi-arid environments in South America, where savannas are dominated by deciduous species, whereas RGR is greater in humid than in semi-arid environments in Australia, where savannas are dominated by evergreen species (Tomlinson et al., 2012, 2013).

Tropical ecosystems are among the most biologically diverse regions on Earth, comprising various forest types that differ in structure, composition, and ecological function. Two prominent types of these ecosystems are tropical deciduous forests and savanna forests, each characterized by distinct climatic conditions and vegetation dynamics. Understanding the diversity within and between these forest types is crucial for biodiversity conservation and ecological management. Tropical deciduous forests, also known as dry forests, are typically found in regions with a marked dry season, leading to the shedding of leaves by the trees to conserve water (Murphy & Lugo, 1986). These forests are known for their high species richness and endemism, housing a diverse array of flora and fauna adapted to seasonal drought conditions (Miles et al., 2006). The deciduous nature of these forests influences their structural complexity and nutrient-cycling processes, contributing to a unique ecological niche (Sanchez-Azofeifa et al., 2005).

In contrast, savanna forests are characterized by a mix of grasses and scattered trees, occupying regions with seasonal rainfall patterns that support both forest and grassland species (Scholes & Archer, 1997). The open canopy structure of savannas allows for greater light penetration, fostering a diverse understory of herbaceous plants. Fire and herbivory are significant ecological drivers in savanna systems, shaping vegetation patterns and promoting species diversity (Bond & Keeley, 2005). While both tropical deciduous and savanna forests contribute significantly to global biodiversity, they face threats from human activities such as deforestation, agriculture, and climate change (Janzen, 1988; Parr et al., 2014). Comparative studies of these ecosystems can provide insights into their resilience and adaptive capacity, informing conservation strategies aimed at preserving their biodiversity.

This study aims to compare the species diversity, ecological processes, and conservation challenges of tropical deciduous and savanna forests. By analyzing the similarities and differences between these ecosystems, we seek to enhance our understanding of their ecological dynamics and inform efforts to protect these vital components of tropical biodiversity Eastern Ghats of Andhra Pradesh.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The Eastern Ghats are located along Peninsular India extending over 1750 km with an average width of about 100 km and covering the area under 11° 03' to 22° 32' N latitudes and 77° 02' to 87° 02' E longitudes. R.V. Nagar Range is situated between 17° 48' to 18°00' N and 82° 02' to 82° 16' E in Alluri Sita Rama Raju district, Eastern Ghats encompasses several hills of different elevations and low-lying valleys. The highest peak of the hills is about 1615 m. There are five major forest types in the Eastern Ghats of northern Andhra Pradesh which are

tropical semi-evergreen, tropical moist-deciduous, tropical dry-deciduous, tropical thorny-scrub vegetation, and tropical dry-evergreen forest types (Champion and Seth, 1968).

Data Analysis

The study was carried out through the stratified random quadrat method. Data were collected from both the Deciduous and Savanna forests. The vegetation analysis was carried out by a total of 20, 30.6 m ×30.6 m sample plots placed randomly from both forests. From each forest 10 sample plots were taken. For herb 1x1 and shrub species 10 × 10 m sample plots were nested within each plot of tree layer. After the collection of field data, used for quantitative analysis by using frequency, density, basal area, and IVI parameters and also used diversity indices like the Shannon-Wiener diversity index, Simpson index Margalef Index (1958), and Pielou Index (1975).

Fig. 1. Location map of the study area; Source: (J. Ramalakshmana et al., 2024).

$$\text{Frequency} = \frac{\text{Number of quadrats in which species occur}}{\text{The total number of quadrats studied}}$$

$$\text{Relative frequency} = \frac{\text{Number of occurrences of a species}}{\text{Number of occurrences of all species}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Density} = \frac{\text{Total number of individuals}}{\text{The total number of quadrats studied}}$$

$$\text{Relative density} = \frac{\text{Number of individuals of the species}}{\text{Number of individuals of all species}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Basal area} = \frac{c^2}{4\pi}$$

$$\text{Relative dominance} = \frac{\text{The basal area of the species}}{\text{Total basal area of all species}} \times 100$$

$$\text{IVI} = \text{Relative frequency} + \text{Relative density} + \text{Relative basal area}$$

Species Diversity

Species richness is described as the number of species present in a sample or habitat per unit area. These are scale-independent indices. The simplest species richness index is based on the total number of species and the total number of individuals in a given sample or habitat and it indicates higher the value greater the species richness. For the quantification of diversity and comparison of species diversities between different ecosystems in various climatic conditions, it is useful to calculate an index of diversity and dominance.

The commonly used biodiversity indices are Shannon-Wiener Index (1963)

$$H = - \sum P_i \ln P_i$$

Where, H = Index of species diversity P_i = Number of individuals of one species / Total number of individuals in the samples

A high value means the community is more diverse.

The Simpson Index, developed by Edward H. Simpson (1949) serves as an index of dominance in ecological communities. It attains a maximum value of 1 when there is complete dominance by a single species. Conversely, values close to 1 indicate the absence of dominance, with numerous species present, each contributing a small fraction to the total. The Simpson Index is weighted in favor of the dominant species. In contrast, the Shannon-Weiner Index tends to favor rare species. The formula for calculating the Simpson Index, also known as the Concentration of Dominance, is as follows:

$$C = \sum_{i=1}^S (n_i/N)^2$$

Where n_i = Number of individuals of the species

N = Number of individuals of all species

S = Total number of species in the site

A high value means the community is less diverse and exhibits greater dominance by only one or a few species.

Species Richness (Margalef Index, 1958)

Stratified random sampling conducted across various strata of vegetation is a method employed to determine species richness. The calculation of species richness in this context involves using the Margalef index. The Margalef index is a quantitative measure utilized to assess species richness, taking into account the total number of species and the sample size in a given ecological community.

$$SR = s-1/\log n$$

Where s is the no. of species

n is the no. of individuals

Equitability (Pielou Index, 1975)

Species evenness or equitability refers to the distribution of individuals among different species within a community. The Pielous index is a commonly used metric to quantify evenness. This index, named after ecologist Evelyn Pielous, is employed to calculate the evenness of a community by taking into account both the number of species present and the relative abundance of each species.

$$\text{Equitability} = H_i / \log s$$

Where, H_i is the Shannon-Wiener Index s is the no. of species

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tree species in study area

A total of 31 species of trees ≥ 30 cm (DBH) distributed into 21 families were recorded in deciduous forests of the study site. The dominant families were Fabaceae, Malvaceae, and Combretaceae containing 3 species each, followed by Moraceae, Ebenaceae, Euphorbiaceae Rubiaceae each with 3 species. The rest of the families Arecaceae, Burseraceae, Combretaceae, Euphorbiaceae, Fabaceae, Lauraceae, Magnoliaceae, Meliaceae, Proteaceae, Rutaceae, Rubiaceae, Salicaceae, Sapindaceae, Simaroubaceae were represented by single species. On the contrary,

there were 23 tree species belonging to 15 families found in the savannah forest of the study area. It was found that the family Moraceae comprised the highest number of species (4 species) followed by Malvaceae with 3 species and Fabaceae with 2 species. The rest of the families Anacardiaceae, Apocyanaceae, Dilleniaceae, Ebenaceae, Lauraceae, Lecythidaceae, Moraceae, Phyllanthaceae, and Rutaceae occupied one species each. In the present study, 14 species were common occurred both in the deciduous forest and savanna forest. However, there were 19 species namely *Ailanthus excelsa*, *Caryota urens*, *Chloroxylon swietenia*, *Cipadessa baccifera*, *Garuga pinnata*, *Grevillea robusta*, *Haldina cordifolia*, *Homalium nepalense*, *Macaranga peltata*, *Magnolia champaca*, *Mallotus philippines*, *Mangifera indica*, *Neolitsea foliosa*, *Pterocarpus marsupium*, *Schleichera oleosa*, *Terminalia arjuna*, *Xylia xylocarpa*. were re-corded only from natural forest, On the other hand, 9 species namely *Aegle marmelos*, *Dillenia pentagyna*, *Diospyros sylvatica*, *Ficus benghalensis*, *Ficus religiosa*, *Garuga pinnata*, *Litsea glutinosa*, *Semecarpus anacardium*, *Tamarindus indica*. were confined to savanna forest sites only (Table 1).

Table 1: Tree species in deciduous forests and savanna forests of the study area

S. No	Scientific Name	Common name	Tropical Deciduous	Tropical Savanna
1	<i>Aegle marmelos</i>	Rutaceae	A	P
2	<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i>	Simaroubaceae	P	A
3	<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i>	Moracea	P	P
4	<i>Barringtonia acutangula</i>	Lecythidaceae	P	P
5	<i>Bombax ceiba</i>	Malvaceae	P	P
6	<i>Caryota urens</i>	Arecaceae	P	A
7	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	Fabaceae	P	P
8	<i>Chloroxylon swietenia</i>	Rutaceae	P	A
9	<i>Cipadessa baccifera</i>	Meliaceae	P	A
10	<i>Dillenia pentagyna</i>	Dilleniaceae	A	P
11	<i>Diospyros melanoxylon</i>	Ebenaceae	P	P
12	<i>Diospyros sylvatica</i>	Ebenaceae	P	A
13	<i>Ficus auriculata</i>	Moraceae	P	P
14	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i>	Moraceae	A	P
15	<i>Ficus religiosa</i>	Moraceae	A	P
16	<i>Garuga pinnata</i>	Burseraceae	P	A
17	<i>Grevillea robusta</i>	Proteaceae	P	A
18	<i>Grewia tiliifolia</i>	Malvaceae	P	P
19	<i>Haldina cordifolia</i>	Rubiaceae	P	A
20	<i>Homalium nepalense</i>	Salicaceae	P	A
21	<i>Kydia calycina</i>	Malvaceae	P	P
22	<i>Litsea glutinosa</i>	Lauraceae	A	P
23	<i>Macaranga peltata</i>	Euphorbiaceae	P	A
24	<i>Magnolia champaca</i>	Magnoliaceae	P	A
25	<i>Mallotus philippines</i>	Euphorbiaceae	P	A
26	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Anacardiaceae	P	A

27	<i>Neolitsea foliosa</i>	Lauraceae	p	A
28	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	Phyllanthaceae	A	P
29	<i>Premna latifolia</i>	Lamiaceae	P	P
30	<i>Pterocarpus marsupium</i>	Fabaceae	P	A
31	<i>Randia aculeata</i>	Rubiaceae	P	P
32	<i>Schleichera oleosa</i>	Sapindaceae	P	A
33	<i>Semecarpus anacardium</i>	Anacardiaceae	A	P
34	<i>Syzygium cumini</i>	Myrtaceae	P	P
35	<i>Tamarindus indica</i>	Fabaceae	A	P
36	<i>terminalia alata</i>	Combretaceae	P	P
37	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i>	Combretaceae	P	A
38	<i>Terminalia bellirica</i>	Combretaceae	P	P
39	<i>Wrightia arborea</i>	Apocyanaceae	P	P
40	<i>Xylia xylocarpa</i>	Fabaceae	P	A

A= Absence, P= Present

Herbaceous species in the study area

Herb species inventory of the deciduous forest of the study area yielded a total of 11 species belonging to 9 families. It was found that the family Asteraceae has the highest number of species (4 species) followed by Acanthaceae and Malvaceae (2 species each). The remaining families contained one species each. On the other hand, 13 species of herbs of 9 families were identified in the savanna forest. The families Malvaceae, Acanthaceae, and Asteraceae contained 4 species each, whereas the remaining families were represented by a single species each. The study revealed 6 species Grass Species, *Eupatorium*, *Semicoca pusilla*, *Alpinia galanga*, *Achyranthes aspera*, and *Boehmeria platyphylla*. But, 5 species namely, *Sida cordifolia*, *Triumfetta rhomboidea*, *Sida acuta*, *Adiantum fern*, *Senna hirsuta*, were reported only in deciduous forests and 4 species namely *Phaulopsis imbricata*, *Ageratum conyzoides*, *Jasticia species*, *Synedrella nodiflora* was identified in savanna forest only (Table 2).

Table 2: Herb species in deciduous forests and savanna forests of the study area

S. No	Name of the Herb	Family	Deciduous Forest	Savanna Forest
1	<i>Grass Species</i>	Poaceae	P	P
2	<i>Phaulopsis imbricata</i>	Acanthaceae	A	P
3	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i>	Liliaceae	A	P
4	<i>Eupatorium</i>	Astaraceae	P	P
5	<i>Semicoca pusilla</i>	Rubiaceae	P	P
6	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i>	Astaraceae	A	P
7	<i>Sida cordifolia</i>	Malvaceae	P	A
8	<i>Triumfetta rhomboidea</i>	Malvaceae	P	A
9	<i>Sida acuta</i>	Malvaceae	P	A
10	<i>Barleria cristata</i>	Acanthaceae	A	P

11	<i>Alpinia galanga</i>	Zingiberaceae	P	P
12	<i>Jasticia species</i>	Acanthaceae	A	P
13	<i>Vernonia cinerea</i>	Asteraceae	A	P
14	<i>Synedrella nodiflora</i>	Asteraceae	A	P
15	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i>	Amaranthaceae	P	P
16	<i>Adiantum fern</i>	Pteridaceae	P	A
17	<i>Boehmeria platyphylla</i>	Urticaceae	P	P
18	<i>Senna hirsuta</i>	Fabaceae	P	A

A= Absence, P= Present

Simpson's Diversity Index is a measure of biodiversity that accounts for both the number of species and their relative abundance. For deciduous forests, the Simpson's index is 0.9312, while for savanna forests, it is slightly lower at 0.9268. This indicates that while both forest types have high levels of diversity, deciduous forests exhibit a marginally greater diversity. The small difference suggests that both forests support a rich variety of species, but deciduous forests might have a slightly more even distribution of species or a slightly higher total number of species. Shannon's Diversity Index reflects the richness and evenness of species. In this case, deciduous forests have a Shannon index of 2.969, compared to 2.863 in savanna forests. This higher value in deciduous forests suggests a greater diversity in terms of the number of species and their distribution. The Shannon index takes into account not just the number of species but also the proportion of each species, indicating that deciduous forests might have a more complex community structure with more evenly distributed species compared to savanna forests.

Margalef's Richness Index measures species richness, which is the total number of species in a given area. Deciduous forests have a Margalef index of 5.345, whereas savanna forests have a slightly lower index of 4.767. This suggests that deciduous forests have a higher number of species per unit of habitat, reflecting greater overall species richness. This difference might be attributed to the more diverse environmental conditions and resource availability in deciduous forests, which can support a greater number of species. Equitability or evenness, measures how evenly individuals are distributed among the species present. For deciduous forests, the equitability is 0.8645, while for savanna forests, it is higher at 0.9131. This indicates that savanna forests have a more even distribution of species, with fewer dominant species and a more balanced community structure. In contrast, the deciduous forests, despite having high species diversity, show a slightly less even distribution, meaning some species might be more dominant than others (Table 3).

In summary, deciduous forests demonstrate higher species richness and diversity compared to savanna forests, as indicated by Simpson's Diversity Index and Margalef's Richness Index. However, savanna forests exhibit greater evenness, as shown by the higher Equitability index, suggesting a more balanced distribution of species. This reflects different ecological dynamics between the two forest types, with deciduous forests supporting a greater variety of species and savanna forests having a more evenly distributed community structure. The herbaceous species in deciduous forests show a higher species richness and evenness

compared to savanna forests. However, savanna forests have a slightly higher Simpson's Diversity Index, suggesting a marginally higher likelihood of encountering different species. The Shannon-Wiener Index indicates that the overall diversity of herbaceous species is quite similar between the two forest types. These findings highlight the nuanced differences in herbaceous species diversity, where deciduous forests may support a broader range of species and a more even distribution, while savanna forests show a slightly higher probability of species diversity despite having a somewhat lower species richness and evenness.

Table 3: Diversity indices of plant species in Deciduous and Savanna forests of the study area

Diversity Indices	Tree Species		Herbaceous Species	
	Deciduous Forest	Savanna Forests	Deciduous Forest	Savanna Forests
Simpson Index	0.9312	0.9268	0.8988	0.8965
Shannon Index	2.969	2.863	2.349	2.41
Margalef Index	5.345	4.767	2.627	2.578
Equitability Index	0.8645	0.9131	0.9796	0.9398

Conclusion

The comparison of tree and herbaceous species diversity between deciduous and savanna forests reveals several key differences. Deciduous forests display greater species richness and diversity as evidenced by higher Simpson's Diversity Index, Shannon's Index, and Margalef's Richness Index values. This suggests that deciduous forests support a more varied array of species and a more complex community structure. However, savanna forests demonstrate greater evenness, indicating a more balanced distribution of species. The slightly higher Simpson's Diversity Index in savanna forests suggests a marginally higher likelihood of encountering diverse species. Overall, the findings underscore the rich ecological dynamics of deciduous forests and the balanced, yet diverse nature of savanna forests, reflecting their distinct environmental conditions and resource availability.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I am thankful to my dearest friend Dr. Vasudevarao Penugurti Ph. D, Postdoctoral Associate at Duke University School of Medicine, Durham, NC, USA for his guidance, financial support in need, and suggestions on the manuscript writing, and moral help throughout my study.

References

- Barnes, B. V., Zak, D. R., Denton, S. R., & Spurr, S. H. (1998). *Forest ecology* (4th ed.). John Wiley & Sons.
- Bond, W. J., & Keeley, J. E. (2005). Fire as a global 'herbivore': The ecology and evolution of flammable ecosystems. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 20(7), 387-394.

- Champion, H. G., & Seth, S. K. (1968). *A revised survey of the forest types of India*. Manager of Publications, Government of India.
- Eshaghi Rad, J., Farshad, A., & Khosravi, H. (2009). The impact of land use changes on forest biodiversity in Iran. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 155(1-4), 471-481. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-008-0450-3>.
- Janzen, D. H. (1988). Tropical dry forests: The most endangered major tropical ecosystem. *Biodiversity*, 130-137.
- May, R. M., & Stumpf, M. P. H. (2000). Species-area relations in tropical forests. *Science*, 290(5499), 2084-2086. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.290.5499.2084>.
- Miles, L., Newton, A. C., DeFries, R. S., Ravilious, C., May, I., Blyth, S., Kapos, V., & Gordon, J. E. (2006). A global overview of the conservation status of tropical dry forests. *Journal of Biogeography*, 33(3), 491-505.
- Murphy, P. G., & Lugo, A. E. (1986). Ecology of tropical dry forest. *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics*, 17, 67-88.
- Parr, C. L., Lehmann, C. E., Bond, W. J., Hoffmann, W. A., & Andersen, A. N. (2014). Tropical grassy biomes: Misunderstood, neglected, and under threat. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 29(4), 205-213.
- Pratap, D., Singh, A., & Singh, J. S. (2013). Impact of disturbance on the structure and diversity of dry tropical forests in India. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 310, 476-482. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2013.08.048>.
- Ramalakshmana, J. & Chandramouli, B. & Yerramneedi, Rajesh & Padal, S. (2023). Biodiversity characterization at the community level in RV Nagar forest range, Allure Sitaramaraju district, Andhra Pradesh, India. *Journal of Xidian University*. 10.37896/jxu17.12/078.
- Ramalakshmana, J. & Yerramneedi, Rajesh & Padal, S.. (2023). A Comparative study on Biodiversity of Plant species between Natural forest and Coffee agro forest in Eastern Ghats of Andhra Pradesh, India. *Ecology, Environment, and Conservation*. 29. 665-672. 10.53550/EEC.2023.v29i02.018.
- Reddy, C. S., Bagchi, S., & Reddy, V. R. (2008). Forest fragmentation and its impact on species diversity: A case study from the Eastern Ghats, India. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 141(1-3), 273-281. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-007-9898-6>.
- Sagar, R., Raghubanshi, A. S., & Singh, J. S. (2003). Tree species composition, dispersion, and diversity along a disturbance gradient in a dry tropical forest region of India. *Forest Ecology and Management*, 186(1-3), 61-71. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1127\(03\)00235-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0378-1127(03)00235-4).

- Sanchez-Azofeifa, G. A., Quesada, M., Rodriguez, J. P., Nassar, J. M., Stoner, K. E., Castillo, A., Garvin, T., Zent, E. L., Calvo-Alvarado, J. C., Kalacska, M. R., Fajardo, L., Gamon, J. A., & Cuevas-Reyes, P. (2005). Research priorities for neotropical dry forests. *Biotropica*, 37(4), 477-485.
- Sanders, N. J. (2006). Biodiversity and ecosystem function in tropical forests. *Nature*, 441(7093), 835-836. <https://doi.org/10.1038/441835a>.
- Sayer, J. A., & Whitmore, T. C. (1991). Tropical moist forests: Destruction and species extinction. *Biological Conservation*, 55(3), 199-213. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-3207\(91\)90031-G](https://doi.org/10.1016/0006-3207(91)90031-G).
- Scholes, R. J., & Archer, S. R. (1997). Tree-grass interactions in savannas. *Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics*, 28(1), 517-544.
- Sebald, J., Thrippleton, T., Rammer, W., Bugmann, H. and Seidl, R. 2021. Mixing tree species at different spatial scales: The effect of alpha, beta and gamma diversity on disturbance impacts under climate change. *J Appl Ecol*. 58: 1749–1763. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1365-2664.139>
- Seidl, R., Spies, T. A., Peterson, D. L., Stephens, S. L., & Hicke, J. A. (2020). Forest disturbances under climate change. *Nature Climate Change*, 10(4), 367-375. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-020-0746-4>
- Tomlinson KW, Poorter L, Sterck FJ, et al. 2013. Leaf adaptations of evergreen and deciduous trees of semi-arid and humid savannas on three continents (H Cornelissen, Ed.). *Journal of Ecology* 101: 430–440.
- Tomlinson KW, Sterck FJ, Bongers F, et al. 2012. Biomass partitioning and root morphology of savanna trees across a water gradient. *Journal of Ecology* 100: 1113–1121.
- Trumbore, S., Brando, P., & Hartmann, H. (2015). Forest health and global change. *Science*, 349(6250), 814-818. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aac6759>.